

INFLUENCE OF IN SITU DEPOSITING SIZE-CONTROLLED NANO-SiO₂ PARTICLES ON THE MECHANICAL AND SURFACE PROPERTIES OF JUTE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Jute fibers with high crystallinity, high specific strength, and biodegradability were extensively applied as reinforcements for advanced polymer composites. However, the surface flaws of jute fibers not only affected its properties, but also formed the interface voids between jute fibers and polymer matrix. In this work, the surface flaws of jute fibers were successfully filled up by depositing size-controlled nano-SiO₂ particles via the sol-gel technique. In order to enhance the combination between the nano-SiO₂ particles and jute fibers, the carboxyl groups were introduced onto the fiber surface by the carboxymethylated pre-treatment. The nano-SiO₂ particles were chemically deposited as confirmed by infrared spectroscopic analysis. The deposition amount and particle size of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fibers during nucleation and growth process were manipulated by selecting the tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) concentration. The results showed that the surface flaws of jute fibers could be filled up by nano-SiO₂ particles (80 nm-90 nm) with the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L. The presence of nano-SiO₂ particles contributed to the significant enhancement on the surface free energy and tensile strength of jute fibers. Compared with carboxymethylated fibers, the surface free energy and tensile strength of nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers were increased by 17.8% and 20.9%, respectively. This was expected to be contributed to the improvement of surface properties of nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers. Moreover, the possible depositing mechanism of nano-SiO₂ particles onto the surface of jute fibers was proposed and schematically demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fiber reinforced composites as an eco-friendly material had been of great scientific and technological interest owing to outstanding reinforcement properties and biodegradability [1, 2]. Jute fiber was a kind of bast fiber with long length, high crystallinity and large elastic modulus, which was deemed one of the preferred reinforcing fibers of polymer composite [3]. However, large numbers of hydroxyl groups presenting on the surface of jute fibers resulted in a poor interface bonding with most hydrophobic polymer matrix [4, 5]. The poor interface adhesion caused a negative influence on load transfer from the polymer matrix to the fibers thus the excellent mechanical properties of fibers could hardly be exhibited to their full potential. What is more, the surface flaws of jute fibers may lead to the formation of voids at the interface of composites. It was worth mentioning that the surface flaws of jute fibers with abundant hydroxyl groups could be treated as the hydrophilic substrate, which proved favorable site for the nucleation and growth of nano-particles [6]. Nano-particles with large specific surface area and high surface energy could transform the surrounding water molecules to the dissociative state (-OH groups) on the surface of nano-particles, and formed the physical or chemical bonds with the hydroxyl groups on the surface of jute fibers [7]. Nano-particles deposition not only improved the mechanical properties of jute fibers, but also healed the interface voids between jute fibers and polymer matrix.

Several studies had been attempted to improve the interfacial compatibility of natural fiber reinforced composites by depositing nano-particles on the surface of natural fibers, which opened up new possibilities to further improve the interfacial properties effectively. Boulos et al. [8] found that coating nano-ZrO₂ on the surface of flax fibers could improve the mechanical performance of its reinforced cement composite, which attributed to the improved durability of the ZrO₂-treated fibers and the stronger adhesion of the fabrics to cement. After 90 days of aging, the tensile strength of the ZrO₂-treated composite was higher than that of the untreated and pre-treated ones. Tzounis et al. [9] confirmed that multiwall carbon nano-tubes could be coated onto jute fibers using a simple and facile deposition method. The multiwall carbon nano-tubes improved the interfacial strength between jute fibers and natural rubber matrix. The tensile strength and elongation at break of deposited jute fiber reinforced composites was enhance by 76% and 14% than that of pure natural rubber composites, respectively. Foruzanmehr and his coworkers [10] grafted nano-TiO₂ on the surface of flax fibers to reinforce polylactic acid (PLA) composites. The results represented that the physical and mechanical properties of flax fibers reinforced composites were improved significantly owing to the presence of nano-TiO₂. The nano-TiO₂ grafted flax fibers improved the impact resistance of pure PLA by three times, and the amount of water sorption decreased by 18%.

Inspired by the researches all above, depositing size-controlled nano-SiO₂ particles was proposed to fill up the surface flaws onto jute fibers. In order to form a stable interface between jute fibers and nano-SiO₂ particles, the carboxyl groups were introduced onto the fiber surface by the carboxymethylated pre-treatment, which could create the covalent bond with hydroxyl groups of nano-SiO₂ particles. The nano-SiO₂ particles were chemically deposited onto the fiber surface by the sol-gel technique with the TEOS concentration variables. The effect of deposition was evaluated by the deposition amount and morphology of nano-SiO₂ particles. The surface free energy and tensile strength of jute fibers were tested via dynamic contact angle analysis and tensile testing machine. According to the experimental results, the possible depositing mechanism of nano-SiO₂ particles onto the surface of jute fibers was revealed and schematically demonstrated. The nano-SiO₂ deposited jute fibers were expected to be used in reinforcing polypropylene composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and reagents

Jute fibers with the diameter of 15~55 μm were purchased from Hunan Shangke Co. Ltd., China. Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS), isopropanol, sodium hypochlorite and ethanol were obtained from Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd., China. Ammonia, sulfuric acid (98%), 4-two methyl pyridine and sodium hydroxide were provided by Nanjing Share Ltd., China.

2.2 Carboxymethylated pre-treatment of jute fibers

Firstly, the jute fibers (1 g) were washed with distilled water at 70 °C for several times to remove impurities, and dried at 70 °C for 2 h. Isopropanol (10 ml) were mixed with 8 wt.% sodium hydroxide solution (100 ml). Then the jute fibers were immersed in the mixture at 25 °C under sonification for 120 min. After that, 0.6 mol/L sodium hypochlorite and 0.05 mol/L 4-two methyl pyridine were placed in the mixture at the temperature of 60 °C with a magnetic stirring for 6 h. Subsequently, the jute fibers were soaked in the 0.05 mol/L dilute sulfuric acid solution at room temperature for 2 h. Finally, the jute fibers were washed by distilled water for three times, and dried at 70 °C for 2 h. The obtained fibers were designated as carboxymethylated fibers.

2.3 Deposition of nano-SiO₂ particles on the jute fibers

Deposition of nano-SiO₂ particles on the jute fibers was performed as follows: TEOS was mixed with ethanol (35 ml) in the presence of 0.1 g carboxymethylated fibers (the TEOS concentration of 0.07 mol/L, 0.21 mol/L, 0.35 mol/L, and 0.49 mol/L, respectively). Ethanol (10 ml) /distilled water solution and ethanol (5 ml) /ammonia solution (2 mol/L) were slowly dropped into the mixture, respectively. The volume ratio of TEOS and distilled water was 1: 2. Then the solution was kept for 1 h under sonification with frequency of 40 kHz. Afterward, the mixture was under constant and

moderate mechanical stirring for 12 h at 45 °C. Finally, the fibers were washed 3 times by distilled water, and dried at 70 °C for 2 h.

2.4 Characterization

2.4.1 Morphology analysis

To observe the effect of different treatments on the jute fiber surface, control fibers, carboxymethylated fibers and nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers were observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM, Quanta 200 FEG, FEI Co., United States). All the samples were gold coated prior to the observation.

2.4.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The absorption spectra of control fibers, carboxymethylated fibers and nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers were recorded with a FT-IR spectrometer (Nicolet Nexus 870, Nicolet Co., United States), from wave numbers of 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. The samples of FT-IR analysis were composed of the fiber powder and KBr powder.

2.4.3 The test of deposition amount

To characterize the quality of deposition, the fiber samples before the deposition were pre-dried for 2 h at 70 °C, placed and weighed in an electronic balance (0.0001 g precision). After deposition, the fiber samples were dried and weighed by the same method. The deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles was then calculated by equation (1).

$$m (\%) = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{m_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where m is the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles, m_1 is the weight of fiber samples before the deposition, m_2 is the weight of fiber samples after the deposition.

2.4.4 Wettability test

The contact angle of control fibers, carboxymethylated fibers and nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers were measured by a dynamic contact angle meter (JC2000D7M, Beijing Zhongyi technology Co., Ltd, China). Distilled water and ethylene glycol were selected as the test liquids. The average values of contact angle were calculated by 5 samples. According to Young's equation (2-4), the surface energy of fiber samples with different treatments could be calculated directly by contact angles [11, 12].

$$\gamma_{1_1} (1 + \cos \theta_1) = 2\sqrt{\gamma_f^p \gamma_{1_1}^p} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_f^d \gamma_{1_1}^d} \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_{1_2} (1 + \cos \theta_2) = 2\sqrt{\gamma_f^p \gamma_{1_2}^p} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_f^d \gamma_{1_2}^d} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_f = \gamma_f^p + \gamma_f^d \quad (4)$$

Where γ_f is the surface free energy of fiber sample, γ_{1_1} (72.8 mN/m) is the surface free energy of distilled water, γ_{1_2} (48.0 mN/m) is the surface free energy of ethylene glycol, $\gamma_{1_1}^d$ (21.8 mN/m) is the dispersion component of distilled water, $\gamma_{1_2}^d$ (29.0 mN/m) is the dispersion component of ethylene glycol, $\gamma_{1_1}^p$ (51.0 mN/m) is the polar component of distilled water, $\gamma_{1_2}^p$ (19.0 mN/m) is the polar component of ethylene glycol.

2.4.5 Tensile test

A fiber tensile testing machine (YG001A, Hongda Co. Ltd., China) with 100 cN load cell was employed to measure the tensile strength of a single fiber at a gauge length of 10 mm and the across-head speed of 5 mm/min. The pre-tension of testing was 0.25 cN. Single fibers were separated from bundle fibers. At least 40 single fibers in each kind of the sample were prepared for the measurement. The fiber diameter was measured by optical microscopy, and the diameter value measured at three different locations along the fiber length were used to obtain the mean diameter of jute fibers. Then the cross section area was calculated by the mean diameter.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of carboxymethylated pre-treatment on the surface of jute fibers for depositing nano-SiO₂ particles

Fig. 1 Effect of depositing nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fibers with carboxymethylated pre-treatment

It could be seen in Fig. 1 (a) that the surface of control fiber was covered with the waxy substance. After the carboxymethylated pre-treatment, the surface morphology was obviously changed, and the surface flaws of jute fibers were visibly seen in Fig. 1 (b). From Fig. 1 (c), nano-SiO₂ particles were mainly deposited in the surface flaws of jute fibers.

Depositing nano-SiO₂ particles onto jute fiber surface belonged to heterogeneous nucleation, according to the equations of homogeneous nucleation and heterogeneous nucleation (5-8) [13, 14], as follows:

$$\Delta G_1 = -\frac{4}{V} \pi r^3 K_B T \ln(S) + 4\pi r^2 \gamma \quad (5)$$

$$r^* = \frac{2V\gamma}{3K_B T \ln(S)} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G_2 = \frac{1}{4}(2 - 3\cos\theta + \cos^3\theta) \Delta G_1 \quad (7)$$

$$f(\theta) = \frac{1}{4}(2 - 3\cos\theta + \cos^3\theta) \quad (8)$$

where ΔG (ΔG_1 for the homogeneous nucleation, and ΔG_2 for the heterogeneous nucleation) is the sum of the free energy of a new volume formation and a new surface created, V is the molecular volume of the precipitated species, r is the radius of the nucleus, r^* is the critical radius of the nucleus, K_B is the Boltzmann constant, S is the saturation ratio, γ is the surface free energy per unit surface area, $f(\theta)$ is the surface factor, θ is the contact angle between the nucleus and substrate.

(a) Illustration of the heterogeneous nucleation

(b) Influence of substrate with different shapes on the surface morphology of nucleation

Fig.2 Schematic mechanism of the heterogeneous nucleation [15]

According to equation (7) and (8), as $0^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$, $f(\theta) < 1$, the free energy of heterogeneous nucleation was lower than the free energy of homogeneous nucleation under the same condition. Therefore, the free energy of heterogeneous nucleation on the jute fiber surface could be decreased resulting in promoting the nucleation of nano-SiO₂ particles. The nucleus on the surface of jute fibers appeared like a hemisphere as shown in Fig. 2 (a), which attributed to the interfacial tension of jute fibers [15]. According to previous researches [16, 17], when the contact angle was constant, the free energy of nucleation was lowest in a concave surface among convex surface, plane surface and concave surface. It meant that the surface flaws of jute fibers were favorable for the nucleation and growth of nano-SiO₂ particles, as Fig. 2 (b) showed.

3.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analysis

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectra of control fibers, carboxymethylated fibers and nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers.

The change of chemical groups with different treatments was assessed by FT-IR analysis, as Fig. 3 exhibited. The peak around 1735 cm^{-1} was disappeared after the carboxymethylated treatment, indicating the removal of waxy substance [18]. The result was consistent with the analysis of SEM. What is more, the peak of 1611 cm^{-1} related to the carboxyl group was increased, which suggested that the carboxyl group was introduced onto the surface of jute fibers [19]. The process of carboxymethylation was shown in equation (9-11). Introducing carboxyl group onto the surface of jute fibers possessed several advantages: (i) increasing the deposition sites for nano-SiO₂ particles, (ii) enhancing the combination between the jute fibers and nano-SiO₂ particles.

After nano-SiO₂ particles deposition, the new peak at 452 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} related to Si-O-Si bending vibration and symmetric vibration of nano-SiO₂ particles were obviously detected, which suggested that TEOS was hydrolyzed and condensed on the surface of jute fibers as equation (12) and (13) showed [20]. The presence of C-O-Si peak (1072 cm^{-1}) could be confirmed that the occurrence of a chemical reaction between the -COOH (on jute fibers) and -OH (on nano-SiO₂ particles) as equation (14) displayed [21]. The chemical bonding between jute fibers and nano-SiO₂ particles provided a debonding force much higher than van der Waals forces, consistence with the deposition design. Moreover, the characteristic band of carboxyl group (1630 cm^{-1}) on nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers shifted contributing to the formation of C-O-Si peak.

3.3 Evaluation of TEOS concentrations for nano-SiO₂ particles depositing on the surface of jute fibers

Fig. 4. Morphology of nano-SiO₂ particles with different TEOS concentrations.

TEOS concentrations (mol·L ⁻¹)	Range of particle size (nm)	Deposition amount (%)
0.07	60-80	2.12
0.21	80-90	10.23
0.35	40-160	13.61
0.49	40-60	15.91

Table 1: Effects of deposition with different TEOS concentrations on the particle size and deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles

As shown in Fig. 4 and table 1, the deposition amount and particle diameter of nano-SiO₂ particles were both increased gradually as the increase of TEOS concentrations. The nano-SiO₂ sol with several nano-SiO₂ particles was deposited on the surface of jute fiber as the TEOS concentration of 0.07 mol/L. The nucleation of nano-SiO₂ particles was hard to happen due to the low concentration of TEOS, which limited the number of nano-SiO₂ particles and deposition amount. With the increase of TEOS concentrations, the deposition amount and the particle size changed significantly. The surface flaws were filled up by the dispersed nano-SiO₂ particles gradually with the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L, as Fig. 4 (b) displayed. In addition, the nano-SiO₂ particles with suitable particle size (80-90 nm) were self-assembled three-dimensional array in the surface flaws of jute fibers, which could enhance the mechanical and surface properties of jute fibers. With the TEOS concentration continued to increase, the limited nucleation sites were gradually been occupied by nano-SiO₂ particles with the increase of TEOS concentrations. The nano-SiO₂ particles with the wilder range of particle size (40-160 nm) were deposited on the smooth surface of jute fibers. It was worth noting that the new defects between the nano-SiO₂ particles were formed on the fiber surface. High TEOS concentration could provide more energy for nucleation of nano-SiO₂ particles (15.91%), which consumed the energy for

the growth of nano-SiO₂ particles (40-60 nm). In order to eliminate the high energy surfaces, nano-SiO₂ particles aggregated seriously on the fiber surface as TEOS concentration of 0.49 mol/L. It suggested that the excessive TEOS concentration possessed negative effect on the particle size distribution of nano-SiO₂ particles.

3.4 Depositing mechanism of size-controlled nano-SiO₂ particles onto the the surface of jute fibers

(a) Preparation of nano-SiO₂ particles by the method of sol-gel

(b) Illustration of the overall free energy ΔG as a function of the growth particle size r

Fig.5 Schematic illustrating the deposition mechanism of nano-SiO₂ onto the surface of jute fibers

According to the results mentioned above, the possible depositing mechanism of size-controlled nano-SiO₂ particles onto the surface of jute fibers was proposed and schematically demonstrated in Fig.5. Hydrolysis and condensation of the TEOS in the presence of the catalyst of ammonia triggered cross-linking reactions with the formation of nano-SiO₂ sol [22]. A part of nano-SiO₂ sol formed stable nucleus in the homogeneous solution (homogeneous nucleation), the other part could be deposited onto the surface of jute fibers through the chemical bond (C-O-Si), as Fig.5 (a) showed. The jute fibers could be acted as efficient hydrophilic substrates for the nucleation and growth of nano-

SiO₂ particles in aqueous medium. Owing to the driving force of the thermodynamics, the nucleation of nano-SiO₂ particles were occurred when the critical nucleus size r^* obtained with a basic catalyst, as Fig. 5 (b) displayed. Based on the previous research, the size distribution of nano-SiO₂ particles was controlled through a short nucleation period that generated all the particles obtained at the end of reaction followed by growth phase [23].

When the concentration of reaction solution decreased below the required concentration for nucleation, stable nucleus entered into the growth phase, the growth orientation of the stable nucleus was determined by the minimization of the highest energy surface. The stable nucleus was biased towards spherical shape, which possessed lowest chemical potential energy. In order to achieve the growth, the nucleus would absorb new nucleus which the size was smaller than the critical nucleus size r^* . This process corresponded to the Ostwald ripening [14]. With the increase of TEOS concentration, the surface flaws were filled up by the dispersed nano-SiO₂ particles gradually. When the nano-SiO₂ particles approached each other closely enough, they were mutually attracted to form the nano-SiO₂ array by van der waals force, as could be seen in Fig.3 (b).

3.5 Wettability analysis

TEOS concentration (mol/L)	Contact angle (°)		Polar and dispersion component (mN · m ⁻¹)		Surface energy (mN · m ⁻¹)
	Distilled water	Ethylene glycol	γ_f^p	γ_f^d	γ_f
Control	63.81	55.78	35.31	4.62	39.93
0.07	51.41	36.62	41.26	7.98	49.24
0.21	53.98	39.62	39.01	8.02	47.03
0.35	57.03	44.88	37.88	6.94	44.82
0.49	59.06	47.01	35.92	6.99	42.91

Table 2: Wettability of nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers

The wettability of a fiber surface could be changed by the microstructure and chemical constitution. The surface energy (γ_f), polar component (γ_f^p) and dispersion component (γ_f^d) of nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers with different TEOS concentrations were summarized in Table 2. The contact angle showed remarkable decreasing tendency after nano-SiO₂ deposition, the surface energy was increased significantly compared to that of control fibers.

Compared with the control fibers, the surface energy, polar component and dispersion component of deposited fibers as the TEOS concentration of 0.07 mol/L were increased 23.3%, 16.9%, and 72.7%, respectively. The increased polar component of jute fibers could be attributed to the massive -OH groups of deposited nano-SiO₂ sol, which made the fiber a great extent hydrophilic. In addition, the enhanced dispersion component indicated that the weak boundary layer of jute fibers was covered by the nano-SiO₂ sol. With the nucleation and growth of nano-SiO₂ particles, the surface flaws of jute fibers were filled up by the nano-SiO₂ array, which decreased the contact area between jute fibers and test liquids. Therefore, the wettability of deposited fibers showed a slight decrease as the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L. The sustained decreasing wettability of deposited fibers was mainly because of the changed morphology of nano-SiO₂ particles with the increase of TEOS concentrations. Based on the Cassie-Baxter model, the nano-fluid motion was hindered by a reducing surface coverage of nano-SiO₂ particles [24]. Owing to the wilder range of particle sizes, some gaps among nano-SiO₂ particles contained limited air to support test liquids. Air gaps among nano-SiO₂ particles were too small for the test liquids to penetrate, which decreased the wettability of deposited fibers. Nano-SiO₂ particles aggregated seriously on the fiber surface as TEOS concentration of 0.49 mol/L, which led to form more air gaps between nano-SiO₂ particles. Compared with the control fiber, the surface energy, polar component and dispersion component of deposited fibers were hardly changed, nano-SiO₂ deposition had not significant effect on improving the wettability of jute fibers.

3.6 Tensile properties of single fiber

TEOS concentrations (mol·L ⁻¹)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Weibull modulus	Scale parameter (MPa)	Ra ²
Control	456.20	25.49	2.98	513.68	0.98
0.07	491.70	26.87	3.29	551.74	0.98
0.21	551.65	28.88	3.82	586.60	0.99
0.35	540.17	28.58	3.68	598.26	0.99
0.49	509.73	27.70	3.28	567.63	0.99

Table 3: Tensile properties of the deposited fibers

To evaluate the effect of nano-SiO₂ particles deposition, the tensile properties of deposited fibers were carried out. The relative results were given in Table 3. The surface flaws of jute fibers could be regarded as the stress concentration area impeding the stress transfer. The tensile strength of deposited fibers with the TEOS concentration of 0.07 mol/L was enhanced by 7.8% than that of the control fibers, which attributed to protecting effect of the nano-SiO₂ sol coating on the surface flaws of jute fibers. The Weibull modulus shape parameter and the tensile modulus increased slightly which indicated that the nano-SiO₂ sol was too thin to filled up the surface flaws of jute fibers. As the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L, the tensile strength and tensile modulus of deposited fibers were increase by 20.9% and 13.3%, respectively. The increasing tensile properties of jute fibers could result from: (1) the nano-SiO₂ particles could strongly combine with jute fibers by chemical bonds of C-O-Si, forming a stronger interface between nano-SiO₂ particles and jute fibers; (2) The surface flaws on the fiber surface was filled up by the nano-SiO₂ array, which could serves as a shielding layer to transfer stress and reduce stress concentration, blunting the crack tip effectively; (3) nano-SiO₂ particles which possessed high modulus could stiffen jute fibers and increase the tensile modulus of jute fibers significantly. In addition, the Weibull modulus was also increased which implied fewer surface flaws and more stable tensile performance of jute fibers. When the TEOS concentration was higher than 0.21 mol/L, the tensile strength, the tensile modulus and Weibull modulus were declined. Owing to the serious aggregation of nano-SiO₂ particles, the new stress concentration areas formed on the surface of jute fibers, decreasing the tensile properties of jute fibers. As a result, the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L possessed an optimum value on the tensile properties of jute fibers.

To sum up, nano-SiO₂ deposition with the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L could be regarded as the optimal parameter for deposition to enhance the mechanical and surface properties of jute fibers.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, the mechanical and surface properties of jute fibers were successfully enhanced by depositing size-controlled nano-SiO₂ particles onto jute fiber surface.

(1) In order to increase the combination between the nano-SiO₂ particles and jute fibers, the carboxyl groups were successfully introduced onto the fiber surface by carboxymethylated pre-treatment. The nano-SiO₂ particles were deposited onto jute fiber surface via sol-gel technique. FT-IR analysis confirmed that the nano-SiO₂ particles were chemically deposited onto the fiber surface.

(2) The surface flaws of jute fibers were favorable for the nucleation and growth of nano-SiO₂ particles. The surface flaws were filled up by nano-SiO₂ array with the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L.

(3) The presence of nano-SiO₂ particles could be regarded as a protective layer to enhance surface free energy and tensile strength of jute fibers. Compared with carboxymethylated fibers, the surface free energy and tensile strength of nano-SiO₂ deposited fibers with the TEOS concentration of 0.21 mol/L were increased by 17.8% and 20.9%, respectively.

In conclusion, this study proposed a simple but efficient method to enhance the surface properties and mechanical properties of jute fibers, which made that the jute fibers could serve as an excellent reinforcement to enhance the properties of polymer matrix.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.R. Sanjay, P. Madhu, M. Jawaid, P. Sentharamaikkannan, S. Senthil, and S. Pradeep, Characterization and properties of natural fiber polymer composites: a comprehensive review, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, **172**, 2018, pp. 566-581 (doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.101).
- [2] S.D. Dutta, N.K. Kim, R. Das, and D. Bhattacharyya, Effects of sample orientation on the fire reaction properties of natural fibre composites, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **157**, 2019, pp. 195-206 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.08.118).
- [3] M.S. Islam and S.J. Ahmed, Influence of jute fiber on concrete properties, *Construction and Building Materials*, **189**, 2018, pp. 768-776 (doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.09.048).
- [4] N. Zareia, A. Geranmayeh and R. Eslami-Farsani, Interlaminar shear strength and tensile properties of environmentally-friendly fiber metal laminates reinforced by hybrid basalt and jute fibers, *Polymer Testing*, **75**, 2019, pp. 205-212 (doi: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2019.02.002).
- [5] A. Dong, Y. Yu, J. Yuan, Q. Wang and X. Fan, Hydrophobic modification of jute fiber used for composite reinforcement via laccase-mediated grafting, *Applied Surface Science*, **301**, 2014, pp. 418-427 (doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2014.02.092).
- [6] X. Liu, Y. Cui, S. Hao and H. Chen, Influence of Depositing Nano-SiO₂ Particles on the Surface Microstructure and Properties of Jute Fibers via In Situ Synthesis, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **109**, 2018, pp. 368-375 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.03.026).
- [7] H. Wang, G. Xian and H. Li, Grafting of nano-TiO₂ onto flax fibers and the enhancement of the mechanical properties of the flax fiber and flax fiber/epoxy composite, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **76**, 2015, pp. 172-180 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.05.027).
- [8] L. Boulos, M. Foruzanmehr, and M. Robert, Evolution of the interfacial transition zone and the degradation mechanism of zirconia treated flax fabric reinforced cementitious composites, *Construction and Building Materials*, **190**, 2018, pp. 120-130 (doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.09.104).
- [9] L. Tzounis, S. Debnath, S. Rooj, D. Fischer, E. Mäder, A. Das, M. Stamm and G. Heinrich, High performance natural rubber composites with a hierarchical reinforcement structure of carbon nanotube modified natural fibers. *Materials & Design*, **58**, 2014, pp. 1-11 (doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2014.01.071).
- [10] M. Foruzanmehr, P.Y. Vuillaume, S. Elkoun and M. Robert, Physical and mechanical properties of PLA composites reinforced by TiO₂ grafted flax fibers, *Materials & Design*, **106**, 2016, pp. 295-304 (doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2016.05.103).
- [11] M. Zhao, L. Meng, L. Ma, L. Ma, X. Yang, Y. Huang, J.E. Ryu, A. Shankar, T. Li, C. Yan and Z. Guo, Layer-by-layer grafting CNTs onto carbon fibers surface for enhancing the interfacial properties of epoxy resin composites, *Composite Science and Technology*, **154**, 2018, pp. 28-36 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.11.002).
- [12] G. Wu, L. Ma, H. Jiang, L. Liu and Y. Huang, Improving the interfacial strength of silicone resin composites by chemically grafting silica nanoparticles on carbon fiber, *Composite Science and Technology*, **153**, 2017, pp. 160-167 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.10.020).
- [13] J. Fu, Y. Liu, P. Miao, Y. Gao, S. Geng, B. Chen, J. Tan and Y. Liu, Supercooling and heterogeneous nucleation in acoustically levitated deionized water and graphene oxide nanofluids droplets, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, **103**, 2019, pp. 143-148 (doi: 10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2019.01.016).
- [14] Q. Zhang, S. Liu and S. Yu, Recent advances in oriented attachment growth and synthesis of functional materials: concept, evidence, mechanism, and future, *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, **19(2)**, 2008, pp. 191-207 (doi: 10.1039/B807760F).

- [15] Y. Kamano, K. Kadota, Atsuko. Shimosaka, Y. Shirakawa and J. Hidakaa, Quantitative evaluation on the heterogeneous nucleation of amino acid by a thermodynamic analysis, *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, **200**, 2014, pp. 474-479 (doi: 10.1016/j.molliq.2014.11.021).
- [16] X. Li and Q. Liu, Heterogenous nucleation in a cave with an apex and iso-curvature lateral surface. *Journal of Crystal Growth*, **426**, 2015, pp. 66-70 (doi: 10.1016/j.jcrysgro.2015.05.024).
- [17] L. Dong, X. Quan and C. Ping, An analysis of surface-microstructures effects on heterogeneous nucleation in pool boiling, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, **55(15-16)**, 2012, pp. 4376-4384 (doi: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2012.04.006).
- [18] S.P. Kundu, S. Chakraborty, S.B. Majumder and B. Adhikari, Effectiveness of the mild alkali and dilute polymer modification in controlling the durability of jute fibre in alkaline cement medium, *Construction and Building Materials*, **174**, 2018, pp. 330-342 (doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.04.134).
- [19] A. Biswas, S. Kim, G.W. Selling and H.N. Cheng, Conversion of agricultural residues to carboxymethylcellulose and carboxymethylcellulose acetate, *Industrial Crops and Products*, **60**, 2014, pp. 259-265 (doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.06.004).
- [20] X. Yang, L. Zhu, Y. Chen, B. Bao, J. Xu and W. Zhou, Controlled hydrophilic/hydrophobic property of silica films by manipulating the hydrolysis and condensation of tetraethoxysilane, *Applied Surface Science*, **376**, 2016, pp. 1-9 (doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2016.02.068).
- [21] T. Lu, M. Jiang, Z. Jiang, D. Hui, Z. Wang and Z. Zhou, Effect of surface modification of bamboo cellulose fibers on mechanical properties of cellulose/epoxy composites, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **51**, 2013, pp. 28-34 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2013.02.031).
- [22] C. Wu, J. Jeng, J. Chia and S. Ding, Multi-nuclear liquid state NMR investigation of the effects of pH and addition of polyethyleneglycol on the long-term hydrolysis and condensation of tetraethoxysilane, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, **353(1)**, 2011, pp. 124-130 (doi: 10.1016/j.jcis.2010.09.024).
- [23] S. Yamanaka, N. Ito, K. Akiyama, A. Shimosaka, Y. Shirakawa and J. Hidaka, Heterogeneous nucleation and growth mechanism on hydrophilic and hydrophobic surface, *Advanced Powder Technology*, **23(2)**, 2012, pp. 268-272 (doi: 10.1016/j.apt.2012.01.002).
- [24] B. Wang, Y. Duan and J. Zhang, A controllable interface performance through varying ZnO nanowires dimensions on the carbon fibers, *Applied Surface Science*, **389**, 2016, pp. 96-102 (doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2016.07.092).